

Individual migratory patterns of the critically endangered Balearic shearwater: a multi-colony and multi-year study in the NE Atlantic

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Abstract

Understanding the migratory patterns of declining species is essential to guide spatial conservation efforts. We studied the migratory dynamics of the Critically Endangered Balearic shearwater (*Puffinus mauretanicus*) by collecting biologging data from 88 annual cycles (53 individuals) between 2017 and 2022. Birds were tagged in three different colonies from the main islands (Eivissa, Mallorca and Menorca). We examined the non-breeding periods in the NE Atlantic, where the species migrates after breeding in the Mediterranean. Of all annual cycles, all birds from Eivissa and Mallorca migrated to the Atlantic (n = 78), whereas 80% of the birds from Menorca stayed in the Mediterranean (n = 10). Within the Atlantic, 54% and 41% of the main areas of the annual cycles were located in the Bay of Biscay and the Western Iberian Peninsula, respectively. Additionally, emerging individual variability highlighted the Gulf of Cádiz as an additional main area corresponding to the 5% of annual cycles. Regarding spatial consistency, 27 individuals carried geolocators for two or more consecutive non-breeding periods, of which 81.5% visited the same area annually. Time spent in each main area varied from 1 to 7 months. Earlier arrival to the main area correlated with a longer stay. The timing of outbound migration was influenced by breeding success: failed breeders entered the Atlantic a month earlier (median date = 25th May ± 20.4 days) compared to successful breeders (median date = 30th June ± 22.7 days). These results underscore the importance of long-term monitoring programmes to capture individual variability, made possible through biologging technology, in conserving declining species.

Keywords: individual variability, biologging, geocator, Balearic shearwater, non-breeding period

1. Introduction

Migration serves an adaptive life history strategy, allowing animals to respond to changes in habitat suitability by moving between distant regions throughout the year. This aligns their distribution with different stages of the annual cycle (Brown et al., 2021; Phillips et al., 2017).

Many species migrate from breeding to non-breeding grounds to exploit seasonal peaks in prey

43 abundance or to avoid adverse weather conditions, with consequences for their survival and
44 subsequent fecundity (Daunt et al., 2014; Phillips et al., 2017). Migratory species rely on the
45 availability of resources of different habitats and locations, which can be influenced by
46 environmental changes such as climate change. As migratory species occupy different habitats, it
47 increase their susceptibility during their annual cycle (Robinson et al., 2009).

48 Individual variability in seabird migration is influenced by many factors, with important
49 implications for species ecology and conservation. Evidence shows that migration patterns are
50 affected by breeding status and age (Bogdanova et al., 2011; Hedd et al., 2012; Phillips et al.,
51 2017). Additionally, sex and individual specialisation also contribute to migration variability
52 (Phillips et al., 2017). These seasonal movements can have population-level impacts. For
53 instance, different studies suggest a relationship between the breeding success and migration
54 outcomes, such as the timing of departure from the breeding to non-breeding areas (Bogdanova
55 et al., 2017; Guilford et al., 2012).

56 Human activities significantly impact marine ecosystems, leading to phenological changes in the
57 life cycles of many organisms (e.g. Chust et al., 2019; Lawrence et al., 2022; Romano et al.,
58 2023). Seasonal timing changes have become increasingly evident in recent decades (Thackeray
59 et al., 2010). These impacts are particularly relevant for migratory birds, as current climate change
60 has shifted migration timing (Gordo, 2007). Migratory seabirds, affected by climate change,
61 experience increases in sea surface temperature and changes in prey availability, potentially
62 causing phenological changes in migration (Keogan et al. 2018).

63 Since the 1990s, the increase in biologging studies of seabirds and other marine predators has
64 provided a wealth of information on various aspects of their ecology and life-history, including
65 the striking variation in individual movement patterns (Roy et al., 2021; Wakefield et al., 2009).
66 Studying migratory and non-breeding periods of seabirds is particularly challenging as they can
67 only be captured on land during the breeding season, while spending more than 90% of their lives
68 at sea. Geolocators (GLS), light-based loggers that estimate geographic position based on ambient
69 light levels, have revolutionised the study of migratory seabird movements. The accuracy of GLS
70 tags is sufficient to track the migration of pelagic species and to identify habitat preferences over
71 large areas (Thiebot & Pinaud, 2010). Using GLS, researchers can study temporal consistency
72 and site fidelity of migration patterns within and between individuals (Franklin et al., 2022).

73 We focused on an endangered top predator, the Balearic shearwater (*Puffinus mauretanicus*), to
74 understand migration and non-breeding distribution patterns with the help of biologging
75 techniques (namely GLS). At the European level, the species is endemic to the Balearic Islands,
76 is the most threatened seabird and is classified as “Critically Endangered” according to the
77 International Union for the Conservation of Nature’s (IUCN) Red List criteria. The conservation
78 status of this species is critical due to unusually low adult survival rates that lead to a severe
79 population decline (Genovart et al., 2016). It is a migratory seabird of the order of the
80 Procellariiforms, with an annual cycle divided into two distinct phases. During the breeding
81 season, the species is mainly present in the western Mediterranean. After breeding, the birds
82 migrate to the northeast Atlantic, ranging from southern Spain to the English Channel (Guilford
83 et al., 2012; Pérez-Roda et al., 2017).

84 Specific objectives of the study were: (i) identify individual-level and population-level
85 distribution areas of the Balearic shearwater in the Atlantic Ocean, (ii) analyse the individual
86 variability in the use of non-breeding areas by assessing site fidelity and timing of outbound
87 migration, and (iii) evaluate the effect of breeding success on the timing of outbound migration.
88 Our results would provide comprehensive information on individual spatio-temporal patterns

89 during the non-breeding season from a multi-year and multi-population perspective. These
90 insights have significant implications for the management of declining species, aiding in the
91 development of targeted conservation strategies.

92 **2. Material and methods**

93 2.1 Study area and fieldwork.

94 Fieldwork took place in the Balearic Islands (Spain) from 2017 to 2022, covering different
95 colonies of the three main islands: Eivissa, Mallorca and Menorca. It was carried out under
96 permits from the Government of the Balearic Islands (Permits: ANE 23/2017, ANE 21/2018,
97 ANE 30/2019, ANE 15/2020, ANE 14/22). During the incubation period (March-April), adult
98 breeders were tagged with GLS biologging devices while attending their nests (Table 1). The
99 birds were handled following protocols designed to minimise disturbance. They were captured
100 from their nests, banded with metal rings, weighed, and had their biometric measurements taken.
101 GLS devices were attached to the birds' tarsus using cable ties, ensuring the total weight of the
102 devices remained below the recommended 3% of the birds' body weight for flying birds (Phillips
103 et al., 2006).

104 Table 1. Summary of the number of annual cycles of the Balearic shearwater collected by island and year
105 in the main breeding colonies of the Balearic Islands.

Year	Minorca	Mallorca	Eivissa	Total
2017	-	-	8	8
2018	-	2	21	23
2019	5	3	13	21
2020	5	1	11	17
2021	-	2	17	19
Total	10	8	70	88

106 Nests were visited twice a year to estimate breeding parameters, such as nest occupancy and
107 breeding success. Breeding success was estimated as the ratio of nests with eggs at the start of the
108 breeding season to the number of nests with chick at the end of the breeding season. At the end
109 of the breeding season, adults were considered successful breeders if a chick was in the nest, or
110 failed breeders if the nest was empty. Nests with an unknown breeding fate were classified as
111 unknown breeding success.

112 During the study period, we gathered data on the migration patterns of 53 individuals,
113 corresponding to 88 annual cycles, with 27 individuals carrying GLS for two or more consecutive
114 annual cycles. An annual cycle was defined as the movement pattern recorded from one
115 incubation period year t to the next year $t+1$.

116 2.2 Biologging data processing

117 GLS biologging devices collect ambient light data to estimate sunset and sunrise based on light
118 curve thresholds. Latitude is calculated from day length, while longitude is derived from local
119 noon (Afanasyev, 2004). Around equinoxes, estimating latitude becomes challenging due to the
120 uniformity in day length across the globe (Phillips et al., 2004; Wilson et al., 1992). Geographic
121 positions (latitude and longitude) were estimated from light data following the methodology of
122 Lewin et al., (2024) and using the *GeoLight* R package (Lisovski & Hahn, 2012).

123 2.3 Non-breeding period

124 The non-breeding period was defined as the interval between the first (outbound migration) and
125 the last date (inbound migration) in the Atlantic Ocean. These periods were set individually based
126 on the time the birds crossed the Strait of Gibraltar, using a longitudinal threshold line at 5.6°W.
127 Individual dates were set using QGIS (QGIS Development Team, 2022), and median Atlantic
128 entry dates were calculated globally and annually. A total of 8 annual cycles (all from Minorca
129 individuals) did not included Atlantic entry, spending the entire annual cycle in the
130 Mediterranean. Consequently, analyses were conducted with the 80 annual cycles that included
131 non-breeding periods in the Atlantic Ocean. For individuals that entered the Atlantic more than
132 once, only the longest stay was considered as a the non-breeding period. The Atlantic areas with
133 the highest number of positions for each annual cycle were identified by the 50% UD contour. A
134 Kruskal-Wallis test was performed to assess variability in the start of the non-breeding period
135 (first date in the Atlantic Ocean - outbound migration) among individuals. By averaging
136 individual kernel information, we identified Important Atlantic Areas at the population level
137 based on the 75% UD kernel contour of all Atlantic positions over a five-year period (2017-2022).

138 2.4 Identification of distribution areas

139 The main distribution areas (hereafter referred as main areas), where individuals had the highest
140 number of positions, were identified using the probability utilisation distribution method
141 (Wakefield et al., 2013). This was based on estimated positions during the non-breeding period
142 in the Atlantic Ocean (2017-2022). First, we estimated the kernel density for each individual using
143 the *KernelUD* function in the *adehabitatHR* R package (Calenge, 2023), selecting the smoothing
144 parameter *h* that best described the individual's distribution using the default ad hoc method on a
145 0.25° WGS84 grid. The 50% and 75% Utilisation Distribution (UD) contours were used to define
146 different levels of utilisation intensity, from most frequent to frequent, respectively. We then
147 calculated the population mean kernel density by averaging the cell grid values of all individual
148 kernels and calculating the 50% and 75% UD contours. Based on the 75% UD contour at the
149 population level, we identified Important Areas in the Atlantic following Pérez-Roda et al. (2017).

150 2.5 Temporal use of the Atlantic Ocean

151 We assessed individual use of main areas based on the UD 75% contours of individual kernels by
152 annual cycle and month, following Pérez-Roda et al. (2017). Positions outside the kernel contours
153 were classified as transition areas. Using this data, we calculated the number of months spent in
154 each main area per annual cycle, aiming to identify the timing of arrival and departure, as well as
155 the duration (in months) of the staging of shearwaters in each main area. This analysis was
156 conducted using the QGIS tool *Join attributes by location* to assign individuals to different main
157 areas, and basic functions within the R environment to estimate the duration of each individual's
158 stay in each main area. Additionally, we explored the Atlantic staging strategy by creating a
159 chronogram that plotted the main areas visited during each annual cycle on a 24-hour basis, from
160 the first to the last position in the NE Atlantic. The main area for each bird and annual cycle was
161 defined as the one used for the highest number of months. We conducted a Kruskal-Wallis test to
162 assess the effect of the year on the number of months spent in each main area, with a significance
163 level set at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$. This statistical test was only applied to the main areas with more than
164 5 annual cycles. We also estimated the Spearman-rank correlation between the first month of visit
165 and the time spent in each main area.

166 2.6 Site fidelity and spatial overlap

167 We calculated the spatial overlap between individual consecutive cycles using the *kerneloverlap*
168 function from the *adehabitatHR* R package (Calenge, 2023). Only data covering more than one

169 year have been considered in this analysis. These analyses were based on individual UD 50%
170 kernels generated for each annual cycle. Spatial overlap was characterised using two different
171 indices. First, we estimated the Utilisation Distribution Overlap Index (UDOI), which measures
172 the sharing of spatial use (Fieberg & Kochanny, 2005). UDOI index values range from 0 (no
173 overlap) to 1 (uniformly distributed with 100% overlap), but can exceed 1 if both UDs are non-
174 uniformly distributed and have a high degree of overlap. Second, we calculated the
175 Bhattacharyya's Affinity (BA), a statistical measure of affinity between two populations that
176 assumes that the space used in two consecutive annual cycles is independent (Bhattacharyya,
177 1943). BA values range from zero (no overlap) to 1 (identical UDs). This index aims to measure
178 the interannual site fidelity of individual distributions during the non-breeding period by
179 quantifying the similarity between UDs across different years, providing information on how
180 much distributions overlap in space.

181 2.7 Influence of breeding success on Atlantic staging

182 We evaluated whether breeding success influenced the date of Atlantic entry during the study
183 period. As all tagged individuals were breeders during the incubation period, each individual was
184 characterised annually as either a failed or successful breeder. First, we built a histogram of
185 Atlantic entry dates based on breeding outcomes. Then, we conducted a non-parametric Kruskal-
186 Wallis test to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in Atlantic entry
187 dates between failed and successful breeders, with a significance set at a p-value < 0.05.

188 **3. Results**

189 3.1 Individual and population-level non-breeding main areas

190 The main distribution areas of the Balearic shearwater concentrated primarily in the Bay of Biscay
191 (BoB) and the Western Iberian Peninsula (WIP), with notable variability between individuals and
192 across years (Fig. 1a). To a lesser extent, a third area emerged in the Gulf of Cadiz (GoC) based
193 on four individuals (Fig. 1a & Fig. 1b). Specifically, 54% of individuals entering the Atlantic
194 Ocean stayed in the BoB area in western France and southern United Kingdom, 41% stayed in
195 the WIP on the coast of Portugal and Spain and 5% stayed in the GoC in southern Spain (Fig. 1a).
196 Regarding the dates of entry into the Atlantic Ocean (outbound migration), there was noticeable
197 interannual variability. The median outbound migration date was in late June for 2018 (24th of
198 June \pm 25 days) and 2021 (20th of June \pm 21 days), while it was one month earlier (late May) in
199 2019 (28th of May \pm 26 days) and in 2020 (19th of May \pm 26 days) (Table S2). The earliest
200 outbound date was recorded on the 7th of May in 2019, and the latest was on the 25th of July in
201 2017. When considering individual effects, considerable variation was observed in outbound
202 dates between individuals and across annual cycles (Fig. S1). However, the differences in
203 outbound dates between individuals and annual cycles were not significant, as tested with a
204 Kruskal-Wallis test ($H_{77} = 55.75$; p-value = 0.45).

205 Figure 1. Non-breeding distribution of the Balearic shearwater in the Atlantic Ocean. a) Contours
206 represent the individual 50% Utilisation Distribution (UD) Kernel contours. Individuals in the Western
207 Iberian Peninsula (WIP) are shown in green; those in the Bay of Biscay (BoB) are in blue, and those in
208 the Gulf of Cadiz (GoC) are in purple. b) Points represent the raw Atlantic GLS data, while the polygons
209 represent the population-level 75% and 50% UD kernel contours obtained from the mean individual
210 kernels.

211 3.2 Non-breeding area fidelity

212 Of the 22 individuals tracked over multiple years, 18 birds had data for 2 years, 2 had data for 3
213 years and 2 had data for 5 years. The patterns of non-breeding site fidelity varied among

214 individuals, as shown in Figure 3. Some birds visited the same staging areas in consecutive years
215 (Fig 2a & 2b), while others changed their main area annually (Fig 2c).

216

217 Figure 2. Individual Balearic shearwater examples of non-breeding site fidelity, represented by a 50% UD
218 kernel. Individuals visiting (a) the Bay of Biscay (BoB) during three consecutive annual cycles, (b) the
219 Western Iberian Peninsula (WIP) during three consecutive annual cycles, and (c) both the BoB and the Gulf
220 of Cadiz (GoC) during two consecutive annual cycles.

221 The overlap between years was calculated for birds that exited the Mediterranean for at least 2
222 years (Fig. 3). Eighteen of the 22 birds (81.8%) had a BA and UDOI values around 0.75 or higher,
223 indicating high consistency to their non-breeding destination. However, birds with lower scores
224 did not visit the same non-breeding areas over the years. Three birds changed the main areas they
225 visited (those with BA and UDOI scores below 0.5), and one individual had BA and UDOI scores
226 around 0.5. This individual visited the BoB in 2019 and both the BoB and WIP in 2018. Overall,
227 individuals repeated the same staging areas (i.e., main areas) each year (Fig. 3 and S2), most of
228 which had high BA and UDOI indices. Birds staging in the BoB were more consistent in the areas
229 they used, while those staging in the WIP exhibited more variability, as reflected in the BA and
230 UDOI indices, (Fig. 3). A Kruskal-Wallis test showed significant differences in the UDOI index
231 values ($H_1 = 22.188$; $p\text{-value} < 0.001$).

232 Figure 3. Histogram of the density of a) Bhattacharyya's affinity (BA) index values and b) Utilisation
233 Distribution Overlap Index (UDOI) values. Scores for individuals visiting the Western Iberian Peninsula
234 (WIP) are shown in blue, those in the Bay of Biscay (BoB) in green and the total values in brown.

235 Individuals that do not repeat the same Important Atlantic Area and visited both non-breeding areas in
236 grey. The vertical line indicates the BA and UDOI index of 0.7, highlighting the cut-off for individuals
237 with higher site fidelity.

238 3.3 Time spent in the Atlantic Ocean

239 The time spent in each of the main areas, was estimated for each individual. In the WIP, the total
240 time spent ranged from 2 to 6 months, with a mean \pm standard deviation (SD) of 2.2 ± 1.7 months.
241 In the BoB, the time spent ranged from 2 to 7 months, with a mean of 2.3 ± 2.3 months. Therefore,
242 the maximum stage duration was higher in the BoB (7 months) compared to the WIP (6 months).
243 From a multi-year perspective (Table S1), there was no statistically significant variability between
244 years in the WIP (Kruskal-Wallis test, $H_3 = 1.683$; $p\text{-value} = 0.641$) (Fig. 4a). For the BoB, the
245 median value increased from 2018 to 2020, but the range of values remained similar each year.
246 In 2021, there was a higher variability in the duration spent in the BoB (Fig. 4b), but overall, there
247 was no significant interannual variability in the time spent in this staging area (Kruskal Wallis
248 test, $H_3 = 2.983$; $p\text{-value} = 0.394$).

249 Figure 4. Violin plots describing the time spent (months) by Balearic shearwater in (a) the Bay of Biscay
250 (BoB) and (b) the Western Iberian Peninsula (WIP) per year.

251 Overall, individuals arriving earlier (i.e. the first month of detection) in the IAAs (Fig. 5) spent
252 significantly more time in these areas.

253 Figure 5. Correlation between the first month of detection and the time spent in (a) the Bay of Biscay
254 (BoB; Spearman correlation $r = -0,79$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$) and b) the Western Iberian Peninsula (WIP; $r = -$
255 $0,85$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$).

256 3.4 Breeding success

257 We compared the Atlantic entry dates based on breeding success for each annual cycle (Fig. 6).
258 The histogram displayed a bimodal distribution of breeding success. The Kruskal-Wallis test

259 showed a statistically significant difference between successful and failed breeders ($H_1 = 10.147$;
260 p -value < 0.001). Failed breeders entered the Atlantic Ocean a month earlier (median date = 25th
261 May ± 20.4 days) than successful breeders (median date = 30th June ± 22.7 days).

262 Figure 6. Distribution of Atlantic entry dates (outbound migration) of Balearic shearwater according to
263 breeding success (i.e., presence or absence of a chick at the end of the breeding season for successful or
264 failed breeders, respectively).

265 4. DISCUSSION

266 This study provides novel insights into the individual differences and migratory patterns of the
267 Balearic shearwater, adopting a multi-population and multi-year approach through biologging
268 technologies. For species facing significant global threats, understanding their distribution is
269 essential for designing effective conservation strategies within key areas used. This research, by
270 focusing on the individual variability during the non-breeding period, delivers essential ecological
271 knowledge for the effective management of the Balearic shearwater. These findings can directly
272 targeted conservation actions, enhancing the protection measures for this critically endangered
273 species.

274 During the non-breeding Atlantic period, the BoB received the highest percentage of visits,
275 followed by the WIP and the GOC, representing 54%, 41% and 5% of the annual cycles,
276 respectively. These three main Atlantic distribution areas identified in this study align with
277 previously identified non-breeding areas for this species based on GLS data (Guilford et al., 2012;
278 Lewin et al., 2024; Meier et al. 2017; Pérez-Roda et al., 2017). Similar non-breeding areas have
279 been identified using complementary data types, such as at-sea surveys that locate regions with
280 high bird aggregations. For instance, Jones et al. (2014) observed large aggregations (hundreds to
281 thousands) of Balearic shearwaters foraging in the large shallow bays of northern Brittany across
282 all survey years (2007-2010), while Phillips et al. (2021) found a high probability of occurrence
283 around the Celtic Sea. Further at-sea surveys conducted in the BoB have noted high densities of
284 the species in the coastal regions of southern Brittany (Astarloa et al., 2021; Authier et al., 2018).
285 In the WIP, Araújo et al. (2017) documented a consistent selection of preferential habitats along
286 the Portuguese coast, with significant bird concentrations between Porto and Figueira da Foz,
287 around the island of Berlanga and at Cape Raso. In the GoC, at-sea surveys identified high
288 densities of Balearic shearwaters near the estuary of the Guadalquivir River (Arroyo et al., 2020).

289 Among the environmental factors affecting the distribution of the Balearic shearwater within the
290 three main areas, bathymetry and proximity to the coast have been identified as the main
291 physiographic factors. The species is more concentrated in shallow areas of the continental shelf
292 close to coastal regions (Araújo et al., 2017; de la Cruz et al., 2021; Jones et al., 2014).
293 Chlorophyll *a* concentration has also been identified as a key factor describing the distribution of
294 the species in the WIP and the BoB (Araújo et al., 2017; Pérez-Roda et al., 2017). Conversely, in
295 the GoC, De La Cruz et al. (2022) found that the distribution of the species was mainly driven by
296 trophic resources, namely pelagic fish species.

297 During migration, seabirds stop at specific marine regions to replenish their energy reserves
298 (Stenhouse et al., 2012). For the case of the Balearic shearwater, Meier et al. (2017) studied the
299 spatial differences in diet between the WIP and the BoB, noting that the distribution of the species
300 was influenced by food availability. These authors found that the diet in the western Iberian
301 Peninsula is dominated by pelagic fish, while birds foraging in the Bay of Biscay consume both
302 pelagic and demersal prey, with the latter presumably often coming from fisheries discards. This
303 is important because the proportion of individuals present in the BoB during the non-breeding
304 season is increasing (Lewin et al. 2024), and the nutritional value of demersal fish is lower than

305 that of natural pelagic prey (Arcos & Oro, 2002). Consequently, this dietary shift could lead to
306 poorer nutritional status and potentially impact the overall health (Grémillet et al., 2008).

307 Seabirds spend 90% of their lifetime at sea, a largely unpredictable environment, and foraging at
308 spatially and temporally predictable sites increases their foraging opportunities (Leandri-Breton
309 et al. 2021). Foraging site fidelity is a common behavioural trait among seabirds, likely related to
310 resource quality and spatial and temporal predictability (Leandri-Breton et al., 2021; Beal et al.,
311 2023). There is a general pattern of repeatability among migratory seabirds, using the same marine
312 areas throughout their annual cycle (Léandri-Breton et al., 2021; Merkel et al., 2021). The
313 Balearic shearwater is no exception, as we found individual interannual spatial consistency in its
314 foraging destinations, with most individuals visiting the same IAAs year after year. This
315 behaviour suggests that Balearic shearwaters select their non-breeding foraging destinations
316 based on the predictable distribution of resources, returning to sites with available food resources,
317 and benefiting from site familiarity and memory (Lewin et al. 2024). In addition, various intrinsic
318 factors such as breeding status, sex or age can lead to individual differences in seabird movement
319 patterns and behaviour (Phillips et al., 2017).

320 Despite the observed individual site fidelity, climate change may be driving a northward
321 migration shift within the IAAs described in this study. Indeed, the proportion of individuals
322 visiting the BoB and WIP has changed, with more individuals visiting the BoB over the last
323 decade (Lewin et al., 2024). Previous studies analysing the migration pattern of the species over
324 an annual cycle (2010-2012) identified the WIP as the main area visited during the non-breeding
325 season, followed by the BoB (Pérez-Roda et al. 2017, Guilford et al. 2012). This contrasts with
326 the results of this work, with a higher proportion of individuals wintering in the BoB. The
327 evidence for a northward shift reported by Lewin et al. (2024) is supported by the increase in the
328 proportion of annual cycles from individuals visiting the BoB between 2017 and 2022 (e.g., 54%
329 in this study). This northward shift in the species' range could be explained by a response to food
330 availability rather than a direct response to temperature changes (Luczak et al., 2011). Lewin et
331 al. (2024) suggest that phenotypic plasticity in Balearic shearwaters might enable individuals to
332 follow shifting resources in the context of climate change.

333 In this work, Atlantic entry dates were determined by individuals crossing the narrow Strait of
334 Gibraltar, which served a threshold line. We found no significant differences in Atlantic entry
335 dates between annual cycles. However, we observed a relationship between Atlantic entry date
336 and breeding success, with individuals that failed to reproduce entering one month earlier.
337 Guilford et al. (2012) suggested this relationship based on a one-year sample, and our data from
338 five annual cycles support the influence of breeding success on migration dates. When birds
339 experience breeding failure, they begin migration earlier, while successful breeders remain within
340 their breeding period foraging areas to raise their offspring. This pattern has also been observed
341 in studies of other seabirds, such as the black-legged kittiwake (*Rissa tridactyla*) (Bogdanova et
342 al., 2011) and the sooty shearwaters (*Ardenna griseus*) (Hedd et al., 2012). Our findings also
343 revealed an inverse correlation between the date of entry into the Atlantic Ocean and the number
344 of months spent in the non-breeding area, which aligns with previous studies of migratory
345 shearwaters in the Bay of Biscay (Louzao et al., 2015).

346 Identifying the main distribution areas and their temporal dynamic allows for a review of
347 conservation measures. The main distribution areas of the Balearic shearwater overlap partially
348 with existing conservation areas, such as Natura 2000 sites (Arcos et al. 2012, Arroyo e tal. 2020,
349 Pérez-Roda et al., 2017). Since this overlap persist across years, these findings can inform
350 management strategies, highlighting the need to protected key areas used by these species. By

351 identifying and protecting these areas, we can mitigate threats and ensure the species' long-term
352 survival. These results will help reinforce existing conservation areas and potentially identify new
353 ones, creating a robust network of protected habitats. Aligning conservation measures with the
354 species' non-breeding period and distribution will enhance the effectiveness of these protected
355 areas, proving the necessary refuge and resources for the Balearic shearwater throughout the year
356 (Guilford et al. 2012, Pérez-Roda et al. 2017).

357

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Preprint not peer reviewed

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Breeding success

- Successful breeders
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Main Areas Transition Zone WIP BoB GoC

